

Micro-mobility Safety Services: Hazard Detection and Speed Regulation

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Abstract. Micro-mobility refers to lightweight personal vehicles with a maximum speed of 45 km/h and a maximum weight of 350 kg. Effectively, this mode of transportation is widely used in modern cities and its safety represents one of the most critical concerns which may affect the adoption and sustainability of this travel mode. In this paper, we present a novel approach for enhancing the safety of micro-mobility including Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) such as cyclists and employees of courier companies. It introduces two data-driven services, Micro-mobility Hazards Mapper (MHM) and Speed Advisory Module (SAM), for detecting hazards and estimating safe speed limit respectively. Additionally, it presents a sensory kit which has been developed to collect micro-level data about micro-mobility. This data is used to train many machine learning (ML) models which will be responsible for detecting various types and severities of hazards, and predicting safe speed limits for road sections that involve hazards. Due to the lack of real sensory kit data, some publicly available open data has been used to test the functionalities of the MHM and SAM. These safety services can be implemented and integrated with a dedicated mobile application to visualize both hazards map and safe speed map.

Keywords: Micro-mobility, Safety, Sensor, Hazard, Vulnerable Road User.

1 Introduction

Micro-mobility is a transport mode that refers to small and low-speed personal vehicles including human- and electric-powered vehicles such as bicycles and e-scooters. This mode of transportation involves a wide range of vehicles and services, and recently has become more popular in modern cities [1], [2]. For example, bicycles became more attractive mode of transportation as they offer great advantages in terms health and environmental sustainability [3]. Typically, micro-mobility users use foot-paths, bike paths, or share the roads with other vehicles. Therefore, they may face various types of risks and hazards such as road traffic accidents and poor road infrastructure. Therefore, road safety represents one of the most important concerns of VRUs. However, micro-mobility mode of travel can be promoted to tackle urban transportation challenges and offer a safe, sustainable and feasible alternative [4].

Several types of sensors can be installed on micro-vehicles and used to collect micro-level data about micro-mobility. Therefore, data collected by such sensing systems may be used to identify safety aspects of micro-mobility including the riding style and behavior (i.e., steering and braking) [5], [6]. Effectively, low-cost sensors including those built-in smartphones can monitor and measure several key variables related to micro-mobility such as acceleration and position [2]. However, more advanced sensing systems are able to collect more comprehensive data about micro-mobility including user behavior, vehicle trajectory, lateral passing distance, and experienced vibration events [7].

Micro-mobility users can face various types of hazards and risks including poor road infrastructure, road traffic accidents, and conflicts with other road users [4]. These hazards significantly affect the safety of micro-mobility. For example, poor road infrastructure indicates low perceived safety and user riding comfort [3]. Effectively, road deficiencies and surface damage can be detected by using various automated techniques such as analysing vehicle movement and vibrations. Heuristic is one of the approaches that uses sensors data to detect micro-mobility hazards and incidents. Additionally, data collected by sensors may be analysed and classified by using machine learning techniques to automatically detect fall-down accidents (i.e., to alert emergency services) [8], identify incidents and near misses [9], [10]. Moreover, collected data about road infrastructure, micro-vehicle position and speed may be used to improve the safety and comfort of users [11]. Therefore, identifying the impact of poor road infrastructure and dangerous road obstacles on micro-mobility riding experience enables users to avoid collisions and maintaining their safety [12].

The severity of accidents involving micro-vehicles increases with the speed of these vehicles [13]. Therefore, micro-mobility speed represents a key factor in the severity of crashes and injuries. However, speed advice can be provided to the users through an on-bike device or communicated by a roadside unit [14]. Additionally, micro-mobility users may adjust their speeds according to the road characteristics and traffic conditions to enhance the safety of all road users [13].

Nowadays, smartphones with built-in sensors may be used to record videos and collect micro-mobility related data such as acceleration, angular velocity, orientation, and location [15]. Additionally, threshold based approaches and machine learning technologies may use this data to detect bicycle fall accidents, road and traffic conditions, and factors that may lead to accident [16], [17]. However, Data collected by built-in sensors is very limited and not as accurate as discrete sensors, so smartphone sensors data may be used to detect specific types of hazards depending on offered data types. Therefore, this study presents a sensory kit which has been developed to collect a wide range of micro-level data to be used as input to the proposed approach. Additionally, this paper provides two real time micro-mobility safety services, the MHM and SAM. The MHM detects several types (e.g., potholes and obstacles) and severities (i.e., low, medium or high) of hazards while the SAM supports micro-mobility users to minimise risks that may lead to accidents. These services are responsible for providing real time warnings to micro-mobility users about potential hazards and related safe speed limits. Therefore, micro-mobility users can be notified by detected hazards and advised to decelerate when approaching these hazards.

2 Micro-mobility Sensory Kit

A micro-mobility sensory kit has been developed by combining several sensors and devices including motion (i.e., accelerometers and gyroscopes), environment (i.e., temperature and humidity) and positioning (i.e., Global Navigation Satellite System – GNSS) sensors. It integrates several sensors and microcontrollers which will be able to collect heterogeneous contextual, vehicle handling, kinematics and environmental data. In the micro-mobility sensory kit architecture (Fig. 1), Portenta H7 microcontroller represents the central control and the main data processing unit. Additionally, Nicla Sense ME board is responsible for collecting and transmitting (to the Portenta H7) different environmental and motion-related data. Therefore, data related to riding behavior, movements, temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, and air quality can be collected and used to detect changes in speed, orientation, and stability. Furthermore, the GNSS provides highly accurate location data while the Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) technology measures the proximity of micro-vehicles to the surrounding objects. Some parts of this system are fitted in a suitable case and get power from a portable and high-capacity power bank. Additionally, data collected by this sensory kit will be either stored in a Secure Digital (SD) card or uploaded to the cloud.

Fig. 1. The architecture of the sensory kit as part of the proposed approach

3 Micro-mobility Hazards Mapper

The Micro-mobility Hazards Mapper (MHM) has been designed and developed to detect various types of road and traffic hazards by identifying areas with specific infrastructure deficiencies (e.g., potholes and obstacles) and high numbers of vehicle conflicts (e.g., heavy traffic). Additionally, it can identify the level of severity of the detected hazards (i.e., low, medium and high). Therefore, it provides a relevant hazards map and it can be used to warn micro-mobility users about potential hazards which may destabilise micro-vehicles or accumulatively lead to a potential crash. The architecture of the MHM (Fig. 2) includes the sensory kit for data collection, data processing, feature extraction, data labelling, and machine learning models training to generate hazards detection models. Therefore, the MHM service facilitates continuous monitoring of micro-mobility and road conditions, detecting various types and severities of hazards, and providing real time map of micro-mobility hazards. First, data

collected by the sensory kit will be processed to ensure their readiness for the following procedures of the MHM. Therefore, data resampling, reorientation, filtering and segmentation may be applied. Hence, collected data signals will be resampled at a specific frequency and undesirable data frequencies will be removed. In the MHM, one-second sliding window has been adopted and used to divide the processed data as basis for the following procedures and steps of the architecture.

Fig. 2. The architecture of the Micro-mobility Hazards Mapper

For the purpose of training machine learning models, data features could be more efficient and informative than the data itself. Therefore, various statistical variables in the time domain can be extracted and used including maximum, minimum, standard deviation and average. Mainly, standard deviation and minimum features of sensory kit data will be calculated for each one-second data and used in the MHM. This input data is unlabeled, so one-second data samples need to be labeled by encountered hazards, if there are any, before it can be used to train machine learning models. Therefore, machine learning technologies (i.e., K-Means clustering) have been used to label data samples in terms of hazard type and severity. The logic of the labeling process is based on some assumptions such as micro-vehicles experience high lateral acceleration when trying to avoid obstacles and high vertical acceleration when moving over potholes. Additionally, the level of hazard severity has been linked to the amount of change in the relevant variable value (i.e., acceleration). Consequently, this labelled data has been used to train some machine learning models which will be saved and used for real time micro-mobility hazards detection. Each machine learning model will be responsible for detecting at least one type (and many levels of severity) of hazards. In the real time implementation of the MHM (Fig. 2 – right side), the sensory kit collects data, this data is accessed and processed, data features are extracted, and the generated machine learning models are used to detect micro-mobility hazards.

4 Speed Advisory Module

The Speed Advisory Module (SAM) has been designed and developed to regulate the speed of micro-vehicles according to projected hazards, road characteristics, and

weather conditions. It provides real time warnings to micro-mobility users about safe speed limits and it aims to notify the users to slow down when approaching hazards. Therefore, it supports micro-mobility users to minimise risks that may lead to accidents. Effectively, the SAM considers hazards map data generated by the MHM, environmental data, and road network characteristics to calculate the safe speed limit for each road section linked to detected hazards. The architecture of the SAM (Fig. 3) includes the collection of the required data, data processing, data labelling, machine learning model training to generate safe speed limit estimation model. Therefore, the SAM service facilitates continuous checking of hazards map, monitoring of weather and road conditions, calculating safe speed limits, and providing real time safe speed map. First, hazards map data (i.e., location, type, and severity of hazards), sensory kit data (i.e., weather conditions), and OpenStreetMap data (i.e., road type) will be collected. Then, this collected data will be coded, categorised, and organised to be labelled by using machine learning technologies. Therefore, for each detected hazard, associated weather condition and road type will be identified (i.e., good, average, or poor).

Fig. 3. The architecture of the Speed Advisory Module

The output dataset of the data processing procedure includes potential hazards, weather condition, and road type. However, this data is unlabeled, so these data samples need to be labeled by the appropriate safe speed limit before ML model training procedure. Therefore, machine learning technologies (i.e., K-Means clustering) have been used to label data samples in terms of safe speed limits. The logic of the labeling process is based on some assumptions such as poor-quality road sections linked to high severity hazards should have much less safe speed limit than other road sections especially during poor weather conditions. Therefore, each cluster includes all the road sections for which micro-mobility riders will be advised to reduce their speed by a certain percentage (i.e., 20%). Consequently, the labeled data has been used to train a machine learning model which will be saved and used for real time micro-mobility safe speed limit prediction. In the real time implementation of the SAM (Fig. 3 – right side), input data is collected, this data is accessed and processed, and the generated machine learning model is used to predict safe speed limits.

5 Results and Discussion

Several types of road and traffic hazards may affect the safety of micro-mobility and VRUs. Real time detection of such hazards enhances the situational awareness of micro-mobility users and enables the users to avoid dangerous routes and risky road sections. Additionally, real time safe speed limits may be calculated for road sections linked to potential hazards and then suggested to users to avoid risks and accidents. Therefore, a comprehensive system has been proposed to enhance micro-mobility safety including a user web-interface developed to visualize the signals related to the sensory kit data. Effectively, one e-scooter and one bicycle have been equipped with sensory kits and then many experiments and test rides have been completed. As a result, the measurements and readings of the sensory kit sensors were stable, accurate and reliable. Data collected by the sensory kit is insufficient to train the machine learning models related to the MHM and SAM since the process of collecting real data to be used for evaluating the developed safety services haven't been started yet. Therefore, some publicly available open data has been used to test the functionalities of these services. This open data is unlabeled and it was collected by sensors mounted on bicycles. Therefore, machine learning clustering techniques have been used to label this data.

The data collection rate of the sensory kit is 50Hz and this has been considered during open data processing step. Additionally, the identified data features have been extracted for each one-second data. Therefore, the standard deviation of acceleration (acc_z), angular velocity (gyr_x , gyr_y , and gyr_z), and proximity (prx_f and prx_r) has been calculated. Additionally, the minimum of proximity ($minPrx_f$ and $minPrx_r$) has been calculated. Suffixes x, y, and z in data variable names refer to lateral, longitudinal, and vertical axis values respectively, while suffixes f and r refer to front and right side measurements respectively. Effectively, the MHM service uses acc_z and gyr_x to detect road roughness and potholes. For data labeling, this data has been clustered into five groups (from low to high input data values): noise, rough-surface road, and (low, medium, and high severity) potholes. However, rough-surface road data has been re-clustered into three groups to find out the severity label. Additionally, gyr_y , gyr_z , prx_f and min_f have been used to detect obstacles and the data has been clustered into four groups: noise and (low, medium, and high severity) obstacles. However, prx_r and min_r have been used to detect dangerous overtakes and the data has been clustered into four groups: noise and (low, medium, and high severity) dangerous overtakes. As a result, three classifiers (i.e., Support Vector Machines) have been trained to detect five types and three severity levels of micro-mobility hazards including rough-surface roads, potholes, obstacles, heavy traffic (or congestion) areas, and dangerous overtakes. However, the detection of heavy traffic hazard type and severity is merely based on monitoring and analysing all detected obstacles per road length unit. Effectively, one classifier (i.e., Support Vector Machines) has been trained to predict micro-mobility safe speed limits associated with potential hazards detected, weather condition, and road characteristics.

The proposed approach and developed micro-mobility safety services demonstrate the functionalities and techniques involved in each service. Therefore, as soon as real

sensory kit data is collected, the procedures and processes involved in these safety services can be implemented in such a similar way that applied to the open data. These safety services can be integrated in a mobile application and used by micro-mobility users and VRUs. Therefore, users and VRUs can monitor the real time hazards map, hear voice warnings when they approach hazardous locations, and receive notifications and advice to slow down when approaching risky areas. This may help micro-mobility users to avoid accidents and enhance their safety and wellbeing during day-to-day travelling.

6 Conclusions

This paper introduces a novel approach for enhancing micro-mobility safety. It involves the development of a sensory kit, Micro-mobility Hazards Mapper (MHM), and Speed Advisory Module (SAM). Effectively, the sensory kit collects micro-level data about micro-vehicles and their users, the MHM detects several types and severities of hazards, and the SAM predicts safe speed limits for road network sections linked to potential hazard. Therefore, the safety of micro-mobility users can be improved significantly if they use real time hazards map and safe speed limit map since they can avoid dangerous locations and slow down when approaching hazardous areas. Since the data collected by the sensory kit is insufficient to evaluate the proposed approach, open data has been used to test the functionalities of the MHM and SAM including the machine learning models training. Therefore, the lack of sensory kit data represents one of the limitations of this study and the next step includes the implementation of the proposed system by using real sensory kit data.

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